

The Place of Democratic Education in Selected Philippine Public Junior High Schools

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Abstract

The research looked into the beliefs and practices of social studies teachers in selected Philippine public junior high schools and the factors that hindered teachers from practicing democratic classroom approaches. The handling of social studies classroom is deemed crucial especially for a nation that has been divided by two opposing versions of history. The study found that the social studies teachers believed and practiced teacher-centered approach and managed their classes using behavioristic methods, utilizing punishment and reward system. The teachers preferred traditional paper-and-pencil tests. The lack of meaningfulness of classroom activity and democratic engagement in the classroom was brought about by the teachers limited conceptions of learner-centered approaches. The teachers needed more training and feedback on their implementation of the K-to-12 program's emphasis on constructivist teaching approach. An important issue that needed to be addressed by the Philippine Department of Education is the one raised by the teachers regarding the social studies curriculum. They deem that the Philippine History is necessary to be tackled among the more mature junior high school students compared to the elementary students.

Keywords: democratic education; Social Studies; Philippine public school

Introduction

The education system in the Philippines has been blamed for its failure to educate the citizens on the dark period of the history during the martial law regime under the late President Ferdinand E. Marcos (Philippine Daily Inquirer, 2016). The textbooks offer limited information and tend to depict the era positively. History professors from top universities of the country have called out the kin of Marcos for distorting facts and claiming that the martial law period was the "golden era" of the country (Suarez, Kalueg, & Mia, 2016).

The existence of a revised history for personal benefit of the Marcoses has caused a divide among the Filipino citizens. There is one group yearning for the return of the "golden age" of Marcos, while there is another group fighting for "never again to martial law". While the martial law era in the Philippines witnessed many infrastructures built, thousands of individuals were imprisoned, tortured, killed or disappeared (Philippine Daily Inquirer, 2016). The era was also characterized by control of legislature, crony capitalism, graft and corruption, human rights violation, suppression of media, and widespread poverty (Klitgaard in Suarez, Kalueg, & Mia, 2016).

Since 1995, the members of the Marcos family have successfully made a political comeback. The wife of the late President Marcos was elected into office as congresswoman of Leyte (Suarez, Kalueg, & Mia, 2016), while the other members of the family have been elected for national positions. Their rise in political power poses a challenge to educators. Do the citizens lack political discernment? How has social studies been handled for the past years since the Marcoses left the Philippines in 1986?

With the weakening solidarity among the Filipino people, the growing mistrust on one hand and growing trust on the other hand of political leaders, there is a need for democratic citizenship. There is an apparent need for the citizens to understand the political issues better in order to make better political decisions especially in times of elections.

The challenge to educate the Philippine citizenry has become higher because the current administration under President Rodrigo Duterte, the mainstream media have been discredited. A big bulk of the people has resorted to the social media for sources of information, but these social media pages tend to present one-sided and sometimes even fake information. On October 23, 2018, the Facebook closed 95 pages in the Philippines due to spam violations and breach of authenticity policies. Many of them were linked to President Rodrigo Duterte's supporters and these sites were followed by 4.8 million users (Mariano, 2018). These followers react and even share the posts in the sites.

Educational institutions play a crucial role in fostering democratic citizens and developing a democratic culture (Giroux, 1989; Apple & Beanne, 2011; Biesta, 2007 in Kung & Kasun, 2013). Students need to develop critical historical knowledge, critical sociopolitical literacy, and application with agency, otherwise they will become ahistorical and will have a narrow understanding of the political, social, and economic systems in the society (Hackman in King & Kasun, 2013). Thus, it would be noteworthy to find out to the place of democratic practices in selected public junior high school social studies classrooms is.

Statement of the Problem

The following research questions were central to the study:

- 1) What are beliefs and practices of social studies teachers that support democratic teaching?
- 2) What are the factors that hinder democratic classroom practices in teaching social studies?

Literature Review

Democratic classrooms are environments where students develop their critical thinking skills (Tanriverdi, Ulusoy & Turan, 2012 in Kiroglu, 2013) and learn how to make decisions autonomously, how to lead, how to tolerate different opinions, and how to collaborate with and respect the rights of others in the classroom (Matusova in Kiroglu, 2013). The classroom environment has eight characteristics, namely: 1) active participation; 2) avoidance of text-book dominated instruction; 3) reflective thinking; 4) student decision-making and problem-solving choice; 5) controversial issues; 6) individual responsibilities; 7) recognition of human dignity; and 8) relevance (Kubow and Kinney in Kiroglu, 2013).

Social studies educators need to be knowledgeable about multiple positions on an issue in order to effectively facilitate dialogues that promote critical thinking (King & Kasun, 2013). In preparing students to become participating citizens in a culturally pluralistic, democratic society, the teaching learning experience should be situated within a framework of inquiry (Cochran-Smith, 2005). The students construct new knowledge as relates to issues of importance in their lives. In doing so, they become aware of themselves as participants in local, national, and global communities whose agency is motivated by concerns for equity and social justice (Santora, 2006).

Although learner-centered pedagogy is mandated in many countries, the reality is that teacher-centered pedagogies still dominate (Dube, 2017). According to Mhlauli (2010), the teachers believe in learner-centered pedagogy but practice teacher-centered approaches. The teacher-centered approach to education is referred by Freire (1996) as oppressive and necrophilic in nature because it suppresses the intellect and consciousness of the learner. In this approach, the students do not have contribution and are treated as objects, not subjects. The teachers and students need to shift from banking education pedagogy to a productive learner-centered pedagogy to empower learners to become conscious, critical, and authentic thinker.

Aside from the approach to teaching and learning, Carpenter (2006) points out that there is also a need to look into the curriculum to make sure that it is not inflated with the vast information afforded by various social studies subject areas. Learning a large amount of factual information trivializes the subject matter to be learned. Thus, social studies should be free extraneous content to effectively prepare activist citizens.

Methodology

Ten public junior high school social studies teachers in three different schools in Quezon City, Philippines were interviewed. Classes of four were observed. The study used purposive sampling to increase the range of data and maximize possibilities of uncovering multiple realities. Quezon City was chosen because according to the National Statistics Office (2010), Quezon City was the most populous city in the Philippines with 2.8 million residents. Three-fourths of the population were enrolled in the city's public schools.

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